

Usability of traffic data for visitor management

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AIR Brief Reports

Key findings

- Data on traffic volumes on motorways and main roads is collected at more than 2,000 counting stations across Germany.
- The hourly aggregated data provides information on temporal progressions, which can be differentiated by time of day, weekday, calendar week, etc.
- What is counted are the vehicles and not the passengers. Furthermore, no distinction is made between commuters, locals and tourists. Depending on the context, this limits the validity of the data.
- Such data allow the analysis of correlations with tourism indicators (e.g. holiday density, overnight stays, arrivals, frequencies at PoI). However, further restrictions must be considered when using the data for tourism purposes.

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Date: May 11, 2023

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Introduction

Issues resulting from high traffic volumes (traffic jams, car park search etc.) are key challenges that destinations have to deal with in relation to overtourism and tourism acceptance. 52 % of people who have experienced overtourism on holiday in the last three years reported "increased traffic" (Bauer, Gardini & Skock 2020, p. 100). 43% of the German population believe that tourism increases local traffic problems such as the mentioned traffic jams and car park search at least temporarily (Deutsches Institut für Tourismusforschung 2022, p. 35). In tourism hotspots, this value rises to significantly more than 90 % (Grimm 2022, pp. 16-17).

Traffic data can make a valuable contribution to the measurement of visitor flows and to (digital) visitor management. In many cases, car park data is already used for this purpose. In this short report we look at another data source for traffic data in Germany and present its usability for the measurement of tourist visitor flows.

Data source: Permanent counting stations on German traffic

In Germany, data on traffic volume is permanently recorded at 2,108 counting stations on motorways (1,227) and main roads (881). The data is collected by the Autobahn GmbH des Bundes (AdB) and the federal states and transmitted to the Bundesanstalt für Straßenwesen (BASt) on a monthly basis (BASt n.y.).

The data is collected on an hourly basis. With the help of the data, the average daily traffic volume (DTV) is calculated for each location. The

DTV is the average number of vehicles in 24 hours related to the respective year of data collection. The traffic data can be accessed online for each counting station and can be sorted by federal state, type of road and traffic type (BASt n.y., please see “data sources and licences” at the end of this document).

The potential uses of traffic data in the tourism context are demonstrated using the examples of Büsum and Sankt Peter-Ording. For Büsum, this is done by using the counting station on the B203 in Friedrichsgabekoog, for Sankt Peter-Ording by using the counting station on the B202 in Kotzenbüll.

There are about eight kilometres between the counting station on the B203 in Friedrichsgabekoog and the centre of Büsum. The majority of vehicles from, for example, Heide or Kiel with the destination Büsum usually pass the counting station, but the location is also along the usual route from Heide to Warwerort, Oesterdeichstrich, Westerdeichstrich and Hedwigenkoog. Thus, it can be assumed that not all vehicles recorded are actually on their way to or from Büsum. Additionally, due to other access routes to Büsum, some vehicles arriving in Büsum are not recorded.

The distance between the counting station on the B202 in Kotzenbüll and the centre of Sankt Peter-Ording (about 20 kilometres) is even longer. Therefore, on the one hand, vehicles that are not on their way to Sankt Peter-Ording are also recorded by the counting station, and on the other hand, not all vehicles arriving in Sankt Peter-Ording are recorded.

Assessment criteria for data sources

Schmücker and Reif (2022, p. 28) have proposed 13 assessment criteria for the applicability of data sources for digital visitor management (Figure 1). Some of these 13 cannot be assessed for the data source discussed in this report (completeness, precision, reliability, transparency) since a methodology report is not available.

The spatial resolution of the data is limited, the temporal resolution is one hour. The latency (time until availability) of approximately one year and longer is too long for a real-time visitor management, but sufficient for a historical view serving as a basis for the development of models. This traffic data is available free of charge and under a very permissive licence (Data licence Germany – attribution – version 2.0) on the BASt website. Regarding data protection law and ethical justifiability, we do not see any problems.

The greatest uncertainty with regard to the usability probably relates to tourism-specific aspects. The external validity is quite easy to assess, since vehicles, not passengers, are counted. With regard to the typification capability and especially the tourism classification quality (i.e., the separation of tourist and non-tourist traffic), the mixture of different types of traffic (everyday traffic vs. tourist traffic) is the greatest challenge, in addition to the spatial discrepancy.

Figure 1: Dimensions and assessment criteria

Source: Schmücker & Reif 2022, p. 28 (translated)

Temporal progressions

Heat maps on frequencies by time and month

The data can be used to determine the most frequented hours and months. This can be well represented in a heat map. For BÜsum, for example, a strong concentration (red boxes) in the summer months and the mid-day/afternoon time is apparent.

It also allows exceptions and peculiarities to be identified. In this case, the month of April saw an exceptionally low volume of traffic due to the Corona pandemic and the restrictions on public life - not only in the direction of BÜsum (Statistisches Bundesamt 2021).

Figure 2: Heat map on traffic volume in the direction of BÜsum (2020)

Months Hour	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
1	382	364	239	155	345	443	473	528	394	643	490	451
2	257	247	170	102	210	270	320	408	305	335	271	235
3	204	196	158	117	290	322	341	374	332	265	216	189
4	272	263	231	151	220	256	283	303	266	263	219	188
5	335	320	253	241	340	479	566	519	458	485	408	359
6	1,472	1,374	1,273	1,001	1,380	1,901	2,107	2,157	1,783	1,138	918	843
7	2,817	2,766	3,165	2,843	3,304	4,126	4,109	3,893	3,757	3,401	3,004	2,647
8	5,440	5,549	5,641	4,147	5,120	7,028	6,784	6,926	6,842	6,287	5,767	5,011
9	4,904	5,342	4,874	3,146	5,038	7,065	8,241	8,361	7,236	6,976	5,810	5,312
10	5,124	5,388	5,266	3,758	6,276	8,496	9,150	9,651	7,955	8,013	6,579	5,978
11	5,537	5,851	5,977	4,354	8,299	11,714	12,138	11,791	11,063	10,931	8,516	7,956
12	7,265	7,285	7,417	5,183	10,048	14,289	15,651	14,084	14,129	13,141	10,198	9,535
13	8,845	7,840	7,917	5,354	10,896	14,811	16,257	14,518	14,146	12,862	10,063	9,301
14	8,887	8,104	7,744	5,404	10,731	14,345	15,763	14,341	13,249	12,213	9,779	8,887
15	8,406	7,960	7,516	5,416	10,177	13,599	15,277	14,377	13,406	12,006	9,543	8,740
16	7,421	7,230	6,730	5,054	8,974	11,904	13,636	12,996	12,033	10,710	8,646	7,861
17	6,585	6,453	5,945	4,785	7,779	10,337	12,075	11,606	10,807	9,926	8,178	7,407
18	5,783	6,071	5,203	3,961	6,777	9,023	10,382	10,520	9,950	9,206	7,609	6,921
19	4,385	4,505	3,725	3,033	5,155	6,758	7,991	8,229	7,542	7,491	6,123	5,585
20	2,866	2,896	2,311	2,028	3,347	4,599	5,332	5,646	4,850	5,023	4,042	3,692
21	1,834	1,861	1,470	1,317	2,483	3,135	3,573	3,914	3,156	3,264	2,590	2,368
22	1,305	1,302	973	820	1,519	2,058	2,412	2,668	1,924	2,095	1,634	1,518
23	1,030	1,026	673	537	1,070	1,326	1,557	1,670	1,352	1,511	1,253	1,127
24	622	640	385	320	582	795	936	906	781	1,013	837	751
Total	91,978	90,833	85,256	63,227	110,360	149,079	166,354	160,386	147,716	139,198	112,693	102,862

Traffic volume by weekdays

The data also allow a breakdown according to weekdays. It is possible, for example, to view this breakdown per month (Figure 2) or over the course of the entire year (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Traffic volume in the direction of Sankt Peter-Ording by weekdays and months (2021)

Figure 3: Traffic volume in the direction of Büsum by weekdays over the course of the entire year (2020)

In this context, an additional analysis of the traffic volume by weekdays in the opposite direction could be helpful in order to gain possible insights into the typical arrival and departure days of guests.

Traffic volume by calendar weeks

It is also possible to analyse and display the traffic volume by calendar weeks. For this purpose, it is a good idea to use the absolute figures (Figure 4) per calendar week or the percentage of vehicles in relation to the total traffic volume. This again enables differences - for example due to seasonal periods - and exceptions to be shown.

Figure 4: Traffic volume by calendar weeks in the direction of Büsum (2020)

Relation between traffic volume and holiday density

A cross-check of the data on traffic volume and the data on holiday density in Germany is also useful to illustrate and identify any possible relations.

Figure 5: Traffic volume in the direction of Büsum and holiday density (per day, 2020)

A correlation cannot be recognised, at least for the example of Büsum - neither based on the diagram nor on the basis of the calculated correlation ($r = .114$ and $R^2 = .013$).

It might also make sense to compare the traffic volume and the holiday density not just for the entire country, but also for nearby federal states or typical tourist source areas of the respective destination.

Tourism classification quality

Relation: traffic volume and overnight stays

The demand for overnight stays (arrivals and overnight stays) is measured using the example of the visitor's tax statistics in Sankt Peter-Ording and compared to the data on traffic volume. The period of observation is the year 2021 starting on 1 May, therefore, after the end of the Corona-related shutdowns.

Figure 6: Traffic volume and arrivals in Sankt Peter-Ording (2021)

Figure 7: Traffic volume and overnight stays in Sankt Peter-Ording (2021)

Time period 1.5.2021 to 31.12.2021, arrivals and nights according to spa tax statistics, periodicity: per day

The scatter diagrams show only a weak correlation between car traffic in Kotzenbüll and overnight stays in Sankt Peter-Ording. The correlation coefficients are $r = .496$ (arrivals, Figure 7) and $.821$ (overnight stays, Figure 8). The last coefficient in particular is surprisingly high, since the counting station is about 20 kilometres away from the centre of Sankt Peter-Ording and the overnight stays do not contain any data on day visitors.

Correlation between traffic volume and visitor frequency at a PoI

If additional data on frequencies at points of interests (PoI)¹ are available in a destination, an analysis of the correlation between frequencies and traffic volume is also useful.

The analysis was carried out using the pier (“Seebrücke”) at Sankt Peter-Ording as an example. An automatised counting system is being used there. The pier is a central access point to the beach. It can be assumed that the vast majority of pier users are tourists (even if not all tourists use the pier). The daily correlation between car traffic to Sankt Peter-Ording and the number of visitors at the pier is $r = 0.779$ ($R^2 = .607$): Around 60 % of the variation in the number of visitors to the pier can therefore be explained by variation in car traffic.

¹ Reif et al. (2023) have provided a definition and differentiations of PoI.

Figure 8: Traffic volume to Sankt Peter-Ording and visitor frequency at the Seebrücke (2021)

Measured value "Pkw_R2", (in the direction of Sankt Peter-Ording), only cars, per day, 2019-2021, pier: Measured value "In", per day

Conclusion: Usability of traffic data for digital visitor management

High traffic volumes are an essential element of the phenomena of overtourism. Therefore, traffic data can be a suitable indicator for the measurement of tourist visitor flows in general and the determination of tourism problems in particular.

Using selected examples of the BAST data, we were able to show that a temporally differentiated and hourly resolved analysis is possible with such data and that plausible temporal patterns and noteworthy, albeit not perfect, correlations with tourist demand can be obtained.

However, there are some restrictions for tourist use:

- **Validity:** Not the number of passengers but the number of vehicles is measured. If analyses are to be made on the number of people, the data can be enriched by calculating the occupancy volumes on the basis of the average occupancy rates² of passenger cars. Especially for the establishment of timelines, this aspect does not seem too severe if the occupancy rate per vehicle does not change systematically. Another advantage is that it is possible to distinguish between the heavy traffic.
- **Latency:** The data can only be retrieved at a considerable time distance from the collection time. This is a significant restriction.

² The average occupancy rate of a passenger car varies depending on the source and use. According to the Federal Environment Agency (Bundsumweltamt) (2020), a passenger car has an average occupancy of 1.4. For travel use, the average value (up to 3.25 persons) is higher (Schulz et al. 2020).

- **Spatial distance:** The validity of traffic volume data for a destination is highly dependent on the location of the permanent counting station. Depending on the location, the relationship between the permanent counting station and the destination or the frequented PoI can vary. Not all vehicles recorded by the traffic counting station are usually on their way to the selected location and not all vehicles arriving there have passed the permanent counting station. It can be assumed that the number of vehicles recorded increasingly corresponds to the actual number of vehicles in the destination or at the PoI, 1) the closer the location is to the destination, 2) the fewer the number of junctions on the way and behind the destination, and 3) the fewer the number of access roads to the destination. Although there are more than 2,100 counting points, it is still relatively rare to identify small-scale destinations.
- **Tourism classification quality and typification capability:** Data on traffic volumes do not allow for a direct differentiation between commuters, local residents and tourists (let alone overnight and day tourists). Nevertheless, it is possible to draw conclusions about the volume of tourist traffic on the basis of the data. For example, the heat maps show a high seasonality, which is presumably not triggered by commuter traffic. A validation and calibration of the traffic data with the help of other data sources (e.g., on mobile phone use) could provide a remedy and enable the missing differentiations. However, these data are expensive. A possible alternative solution would be to differentiate the data measured at the BAST counting stations with the help of external reference data, for example on commuter flows, weather or holiday density (Schmücker 2023). This attempt has not yet been made.

Despite these limitations, the data can be used for tourism purposes. They can provide good indications for analyses and planning (e.g., traffic and parking concepts or the creation and promotion of alternative mobility offers, especially for events or other peak times) as well as a baseline for mobility within destinations. These findings and considerations can therefore also be used in the development of digital visitor management.

Data source and licence

The data used for this document are available from the German Federal Highway Research Institute on their website <https://www.bast.de/dauerzaehlstellen>. The data are licenced under the "Data licence Germany – attribution – Version 2.0" or "dl-de/by-2-0". The licence text is available at www.govdata.de/dl-de/by-2-0.

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Notes

This document was produced as part of the project "AIR - AI-based Recommender for Sustainable Tourism" with partial funding from the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection.

For more information on AIR, please visit www.air-tourism.de/en.

Supported by:

Federal Ministry
for the Environment, Nature Conservation,
Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection

based on a decision of the German Bundestag

Suggested citation:

Naschert, Lisa; Schmücker, Dirk (2023). *Usability of traffic data for visitor management*. (AIR Brief Reports). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7906843](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7906843)

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